

PRINCIPALS' LEADERSHIP STYLES AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN ADMINISTRATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN DELTA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated principals' leadership styles and teachers' job performance in administration of secondary schools in Delta State. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study which was also guided with four (4) research questions and four (4) hypotheses. Purposive random sampling technique was used to select 493 principals and 4,280 teachers, representing 30% of the 14762 population for the study. A 45-item questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point scale: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE) – 3 points, Low Extent (LE) – 2 Points, Very Low Extent (VLE) – 1 point. The face and content validity of the instrument was ascertained and to ensure internal consistency, 30 copies of the questionnaire were administered to one (1) principal and 29 teachers at Aguata High School, Aguata, Anambra State, which is outside the scope of this study. The data collected were subjected to Cronbach Alpha which yielded the following reliability coefficient results for the 4 research questions: 1. $r = 0.97$, 2. $r = 0.90$, 3. $r = 0.95$, 4. $r = 0.97$, with whole reliability = 0.97. A total of 4773 copies of the questionnaire were administered and a total of 4398 were fully completed and returned, indicating 92.14% return rate. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviations. T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings show that democratic and transactional leadership styles are more accessible and influence teachers' job performance more positively than autocratic and laissez-faire leadership styles. It was therefore recommended that principals should adopt more of democratic leadership style and only chip in autocratic leadership style when some tough decisions need to be taken.

Keywords: Principals, Leadership Styles, Teachers' Job Performance, Administration, Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Leadership occurs whenever one person attempts to influence the behaviour of an individual or a group regardless of the reason. It is the ability to get things done by harnessing the support and co-operation of other people within the institution, organization or system. Ejiogu and Ogonor (2016) describe leadership as the process of persuading other people to jointly seek to enthusiastically achieve defined objectives. In other words, leadership has to do with the act of uniting and stimulating followers towards the achievement of particular objectives in particular situations. Those who are in leadership require people of particular talent and ability and not people who occupy positions of authority because of associated benefits or favours.

In educational institutions, leadership involves the process of enlisting and guiding the talents and energies of school personnel, students, parents, community members and material resources towards the accomplishment of the goals and objectives of the educational system. It also has to do with the engagement of school personnel (teaching and non-teaching)

to get involved in the promotion of academic activities in their institutions (Abama, Oladipo & Gyang, 2016). Leadership is thus very sensitive for organizational survival or failure in the education setting, and the institutional administrator is always commended for the success of the school system and is also held responsible for any form of lapse. The school administrator as a leader, therefore, is that individual who exercises more important positive influence than any other member of the institution he is in (Adekunle, 2017).

Many leadership styles are identified in organizations, including educational institutions. These include, among others, democratic leadership style, transactional leadership style, autocratic leadership style and laissez-faire. Leadership style is the reflection of the leaders' behavioural pattern that enables them to manage their employees by directing and motivating them towards a common vision. Leadership styles also determine a leader's approach to strategize and implement methods while fulfilling the business expectations and focusing on the team's growth. Becker (2021) opines that democratic leadership is exactly what it sounds like – the leader makes decisions based on each team member's input. Although the leader makes the final claim each employee has an equal say in the project's direction. This leadership style resembles how leaders often make decisions in institutions board meetings.

Transactional leadership style also known as managerial leadership style, is a type of leadership that focuses on the role of organization, group performance and supervision (Jagua, 2021). The leaders involved with this type of leadership style use reward and punishment while doing specific operations to encourage the workers to do more. The leader does not focus on changing the people's attitude to issues and situation but much more given to achieving the short and long term goals of the organization. On the other hand, Becker (2021) observes that in autocratic leadership style, the leader takes decisions without input from anyone in a subordinating role. This style of leadership is most useful when the organization needs to control specific situations, not as a stand-alone leadership style.

Laissez-faire leadership style also called delegative or hands-off leadership is the least intrusive form of leadership. Leaders who embrace it give nearly all authority to their employees and holds them accountable for their work. According to Zhang, et al. (2023), although laissez-faire leadership is universally considered to be the most ineffective leadership style, a few recent studies have revealed that it may have most or even significant positive influence on subordinate's work outcomes.

Principal's leadership style affects all aspects of the school management, especially the school administration. According to Ngezack, et al. (2024), school administration refers to methodical placement for the implementation of educational programs to accomplish the school's established objectives. Ogunode, et al. (2021) observes that one major objective of school administration is to integrate and coordinate all the physical and human resources efficiently towards a common goal. The roles principals play in secondary schools include providing good leadership to enhance better job performance of teachers and academic achievement of students. How well the principal performs these roles is a matter of concern to educationists and other stakeholders.

The school principal is an administrator who runs an organization for established purposes, but occasionally recognizes the needs of his teachers for the modification of his mandate, and to bring about the necessary changes in his organization to make it effective. Uwannah et. al. (2019) see job performance as the output of person or a group of person's input that is directed to fulfilling predetermined organizational objectives. Many employees feel dissatisfied with their jobs at one point or another. Some employees leave their jobs for better opportunities, while others choose to stay, negatively affecting the organization because they typically lack motivation.

Teachers' job performance include writing of lesson note, lesson plan, organization of instructional materials, assigning of test and examination, marking, representing of school, extra-curriculum activities and motivation of students. Teachers' job performance indicates the extent to which teachers execute their responsibilities in the school, by effectively inculcating the three domains: cognitive, affective and psychomotor. Nwankwo and Ifeanyi (2021) assert that the satisfaction acquired with the work is one of the fundamental reasons for high workplace commitment. Job performance therefore derives from several factors, including principal's leadership style and it permeates the general work environment of the school.

Leadership in education like other organizations is pivotal to the success or failure of the group goals. When two or more persons have a task to accomplish, there is the need for leadership to direct actions towards attainment of objectives. The principal is the leader or chief executive of a secondary school. He leads the team in implementing educational policies in the secondary level of education. The principal being the secondary school manager, could adopt any leadership style as the situation demands to run an effective administration and promote teachers' job performance. Principals' personal characteristics and their adopted leadership styles are germane to the success or otherwise of the group goals. Hence Pardosi and Utari (2022) see principals' leadership as the effort to influence, encourage, guide, and direct teachers, staff, students, parents and other related individuals to work together in achieving set goals.

All human resources of the school matter to the principal, hence it is his or her responsibility to motivate teachers, non-teaching staff, students, parents and other individuals to work together in achieving set goals. All these, certainly call for professional leadership in the school. Whatever angle with which one looks at leadership style, what is clear is that some people want collaboration and motivation for the whole group to succeed together as indicated in democratic, participative, supportive and transformational leadership styles. Principals must weigh the goals, the teachers, and the environmental imperatives before arriving at the most suitable leadership style to adopt. In any case, whatever leadership style a principal adopts is not mutually exclusive to any other leadership style. Time and events influence the leadership style that could work best.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The relationship between principal's leadership style and teachers' job performance has been a subject of controversy among researchers (Nwadin, 1998; Adeyemi, 2006). The controversy has been centred on whether or not the style of leadership of principals influences the level of job performance among teachers. Observation in the school system shows that the style of leadership of a principal could perhaps have serious impact on teachers' job performance.

Providing quality education requires efforts from multiple stakeholder groups, including principals and teachers. How effective principals have been in harnessing these multiple stakeholders and the extent to which the leadership styles of principals have helped in providing the needed quality education, have remained issues of concern to researchers. This is a gap that has elicited this study and which the study intends to fill. The statement of the problem therefore is to what extent principals' leadership styles influence teachers' job performance in administration of secondary schools in Delta State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to determine the influence of principals' administrative style on teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State. Specifically, the objectives are:

1. To find out the extent principals who adopt democratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance.
2. To find out the extent principals' transactional style of leadership influence teachers' job performance.

3. To determine the extent principals who adopt autocratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance.
4. To determine the extent principals who adopt laissez-faire administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do principals who adopt democratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance?
2. To what extent does principals' transactional style of leadership influence teachers' job performance?
3. To what extent does principals who adopt autocratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance?
4. To what extent do principals who adopt laissez-faire administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance?

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses are tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- 1 There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on influence of principals' democratic administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance.
- 2 There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on influence of principals' transactional style of leadership teachers' job performance.
- 3 There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on influence of principals' autocratic administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance.
- 4 There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on influence of principals' laissez-faire administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Empirical Studies

Imakpokpomwan, et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between principal leadership style and teachers work attitude in south senatorial district of Edo State. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. Of the seven local government areas, three were sampled for analysis while 175 teachers were sub-set of the study. Three research questions were raised. The finding showed that secondary school principals in sampled schools predominantly employed a democratic leadership style. Recommendations were therefore focused on sustaining the team spirit existing in the public secondary schools in the district. Kene, et al. (2021) carried out a study on effectiveness of principals' leadership styles in school improvement and students' academic achievement in government secondary school of Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia. The study analyzed zone's school inspection reports on the schools' levels measured based on standards set by the Federal Ministry of Education and Students' academic results obtained from National Education Assessment and Examination Agency of three years (2017 – 2019). The findings revealed that principals' implementations of transformational, instructional and transactional school leadership styles were above average. However, no changes were observed in standards of the secondary school because about 86.3% of the schools were found below the expected standards and students' academic achievements

moving between decrease and fluctuation within the three years. Results indicate that effectiveness of the principals' school leadership styles was not at its expected level in transforming the schools to the required standards and bringing about sustainable academic achievement. It was therefore recommended that extra efforts and commitment should be put in by the principals and other stakeholders to reverse these conditions.

Adeyemi (2010) investigated principals' leadership styles and teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools in Ondo state, Nigeria. The sample was made up of 240 principals and 1800 teachers. Two instruments: principals' leadership style questionnaire and teachers' job performance questionnaire were used for data collection. It was found that democratic leadership style was the most commonly used among principals. Teachers' job performance was also found to be at a moderate level in the schools. Teachers' job performance was found to be better in schools where principals adopted autocratic leadership style than in schools where principals used democratic or laissez-faire leadership styles. It was then recommended that school principals should imbibe a mixture of autocratic and democratic styles of leadership in their school administration in order to enhance better job performance among teachers. Maqbool, et al. (2023) carried out a study on the role of diverse leadership styles in teaching to sustain academic excellence at secondary level. The quantitative research method was used and two hypotheses were formulated. The findings revealed that a statistically strong positive relationship existed among the diverse leadership styles in the process of teaching and sustaining academic excellence. Based on the findings, it was concluded that when teachers increase their effort in the use of strategic, instructional and cultural leadership styles, academic excellence could be sustained and improved.

Okoroma and Agbo (2022) studied the influence of principals' leadership styles on job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Etche and Obio/Akpor Local Government Areas of Rivers state. The sample for the study was 363 comprising 39 principals and 324 teachers. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire. The findings revealed that democratic and transactional leadership styles of principals to a high extent influence teachers' job performance. It was recommended among others that seminars and workshops should be conducted to stress the importance of democratic and transactional leadership styles to principals. Owenubiugie and Ibadin (2017) investigated principals' leadership styles as nexus to job performance of teachers in senior secondary schools in Edo state, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study. 240 teachers were used as sample representing 60% of the population of 400 teachers. The results showed that the respondents agreed that autocratic and laissez-faire principals' leadership styles influenced teachers' job performance to a low extent, while democratic principals' leadership style influenced teachers' job performance to a high extent. It was recommended that effort should be made by government to organize workshops or symposia on a regular basis to ensure that principals understand the individual behaviours of their teachers to improve job performance.

Chinwuba, M. A. (2023) carried out a study on impact of principals' leadership style on school administration and teachers job performance in public secondary school in FCT, Nigeria. Simple random sampling was used to draw samples of 16 principals (principals and vice principals) and 300 teachers. The raw data collected from the field were analyzed using frequency and percentage method. Chi test was used to test the hypotheses. The results revealed that there is significant relationship between principals' leadership styles and school administration in public secondary schools. It was recommended that professional training in education leadership skills and styles is expedient for all institutional administrators.

METHODOLOGY

This study investigated principals' leadership styles and teachers' job performance in the administration of Secondary Schools in Delta State. The study adopted descriptive survey design. This research design is considered suitable because there is no manipulation of data (Okoro 2024).

The target population of the study is 14,762, comprising 493 principals and 14,269 teachers in 493 public secondary schools in Delta State. The purposive sampling technique was used to select 30% of the 14,762 population for the study which gave a total of 4,773 respondents comprising 493 principals and 4280 teachers. A 45-item questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: Part A contained five (5) items of demographic variables of the respondents-Name of School, Rank, Sex, Job Experience, School Location; Part B contained 40 items based on the four (4) research questions. Research question 1: To what extent do principals who adopt democratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance? - 17 items. Research question 2: To what extent does principals' transactional style of leadership influence teachers' job performance? - 5 items. Research question 3: To what extent do principals who adopt autocratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance? - 8 items. Research question 4: To what extent do principals who adopt laissez-faire administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance? - 10 items. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point scale of responses: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE).

There was face and content validity of the instrument. The questionnaire constructed was given to three (3) experts in Educational Administration and two (2) in Measurement and Evaluation at Delta State University Abraka. The experts made corrections and suggestions which were taken into consideration before the final copy was written. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha statistics. The split half reliability method was employed using one (1) principal and 29 teachers from Aguata High School, Aguata, Anambra State, which is outside the scope of this study. The Spearman-Brown prophecy formula was used to obtain the reliability of the whole test (Step up). Section-by-section and overall analysis were conducted on the instrument to determine the reliability of each section and the entire instrument. The reliability coefficient of each of the four sections is: Research Question 1, $r = 0.97$; Research Question 2, $r = 0.90$; Research Question 3, $r = 0.95$; Research Question 4, $r = 0.97$; and whole reliability, $r = 0.97$. The reliability correlation coefficient values were higher than 0.60, which shows that the instrument is reliable and appropriate for use in the study.

A total of 4773 copies of the questionnaires were administered to 493 principals and 4280 teachers in 493 Public secondary schools in Delta State. With the help of two (2) research assistants in each school, a total of 4398 were fully completed and returned within a period of one (1) month indicating a return rate of 92.14%.

The data collected were weighted and analyzed as follows: Very High Extent - (VHE) - 4 points, High Extent (HE)- 3 points, Low Extent (LE)- 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE)-1 point. In decision rule, any item with a mean score of 2.5 and above is regarded as High Extent, while any item below 2.5 is regarded as Low Extent. T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. If t-calculated value is less than t-critical, hypothesis is retained. On the other hand, if the t-calculated value is greater than t-critical, hypotheses is rejected.

RESULTS

Research question 1: To what extent do principals who adopt democratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance?

Table 1: Mean of responses on the extent principals who adopt democratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance

S/N	Items on democratic administrative style of leadership and teachers' job performance	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	DEC
1.	Group discussion enhances teachers' decision making skills	3.19	0.46	HE
2.	Inclusion of Teachers' ideas improves job performance	3.18	0.41	HE
3.	Teacher empowerment enhances instructional delivery	3.10	0.47	HE
4.	Promoting morality improves teachers' commitment	3.18	0.43	HE
5.	Teachers' opinions boost their engagement and performance	3.15	0.38	HE
6.	Encourages creativity and better problem solving	3.16	0.41	HE
7.	Expands teachers' perspective and innovative abilities	3.11	0.40	HE
8.	Improves trust and collaboration among staff	3.17	0.40	HE
9.	Encourages innovation and proactive teaching approaches	3.14	0.40	HE
10.	Promotes accountability and teamwork	3.14	0.40	HE
11.	Enhances creative teaching strategies	3.17	0.42	HE
12.	Leads to improved instructional methods	3.12	0.35	HE
13.	Strengthens relationships and fosters motivation	3.09	0.42	HE
14.	Provides clarity and focus for teachers' tasks	3.12	0.35	HE
15.	Improves teachers' performance and effectiveness	3.16	0.41	HE
16.	Encourages collaboration and shared success	3.08	0.34	HE
17.	Boosts teachers morale and productivity	3.14	0.42	HE
Aggregate Mean/Std.Dev.		3.14	0.40	
Criterion Mean		2.50		

The analysis reveals that principals who adopt a democratic administrative style of leadership significantly influence teachers' job performance. This is shown by an aggregate mean score of 3.14 (Std. Dev. = 0.40), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that the leadership approach is highly effective. All the assessed factors received mean scores above the criterion mean, highlighting their importance in enhancing job performance among teachers.

Research Question 2: To what extent does principals' transactional style of leadership influence teachers' job performance?

Table 2: Mean of responses on the extent principals' transactional style of leadership influence teachers' job performance

S/N	Items on transactional style of leadership and teachers' job performance	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Managerial approach helps teachers exceed their limits	3.21	0.43	HE
2.	Structured leadership makes teachers more adaptable	3.12	0.38	HE
3.	Effective planning enhances teachers' performance	3.10	0.39	HE
4.	Rewards motivate teachers to implement the curriculum effectively	3.11	0.34	HE
5.	Discipline ensures teachers accomplish tasks effectively.	3.16	0.39	HE
Aggregate Mean/Std.Dev.		3.14	0.39	
Criterion Mean		2.50		

The analysis reveals that principals who adopt a transactional style of leadership significantly influence teachers' job performance. This is shown by an aggregate mean score of 3.14 (Std. Dev. = 0.39), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that this leadership approach is highly effective. All the assessed factors received mean scores above the criterion mean, highlighting their importance in enhancing job performance among teachers.

Research Question 3: To what extent do principals who adopt autocratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance?

Table 3: Mean of responses on the extent principals who adopt autocratic administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance

S/N	Items on autocratic administrative style of leadership and teachers' job performance	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Strict control ensures efficient administrations and task focus	3.15	0.36	HE
2.	Enforcement of rules boost task completion	3.12	0.33	HE
3.	Rewards are based on strict compliance and target achievements	3.15	0.36	HE
4.	Strict deadlines improve task promptness	3.07	0.35	HE
5.	Excludes teachers, ensuring uniform decisions	3.10	0.30	HE
6.	Rarely holds discussion, ensuring quick actions	3.04	0.41	HE
7.	Limits teachers' decision to ensure consistency	3.06	0.28	HE
8.	Swift decisions minimize disruptions.	3.08	0.39	HE
Aggregate Mean/Std.Dev.		3.10	0.35	
Criterion Mean		2.50		

The analysis reveals that principals who adopt an autocratic administrative style of leadership significantly influence teachers' job performance. This is shown by an aggregate mean score of 3.10 (Std. Dev. = 0.35), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that this leadership approach is effective in certain contexts. All the assessed factors received mean scores above the criterion mean, highlighting their role in enhancing job performance among teachers.

Research Question 4: To what extent do principals who adopt laissez-faire administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance?

Table 4: Mean of responses on the extent principals who adopt laissez-faire administrative style of leadership influence teachers' job performance

S/N	Items on laissez-faire administrative style of leadership and teachers' job performance	\bar{x}	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Minimal guidance encourages teachers independence	2.92	0.67	HE
2.	Skilled staff handle tasks efficiently with minimal supervision	2.90	0.68	HE
3.	Competent staff ensure smooth operations despite limited Oversight	2.93	0.67	HE
4.	Principals avoiding decision making reduce teachers job performance	2.86	0.68	HE
5.	Poor relationships reduce motivation and job satisfaction	2.86	0.66	HE
6.	Delayed decisions hinder timely task completion	2.86	0.65	HE

7.	Unreasonable actions cause frustrations and lower morale	2.91	0.68	HE
8.	Excessive paperwork reduces teachers focus on core duties	2.87	0.67	HE
9.	Slow decisions disrupt workflow and efficiency	2.88	0.67	HE
10.	Resistance to change limits adaptability	2.90	0.65	HE
Aggregate Mean/Std.Dev.		2.89	0.67	
Criterion Mean		2.50		

The analysis reveals that principals who adopt a laissez-faire administrative style of leadership moderately influence teachers' job performance. This is shown by an aggregate mean score of 2.89 (Std. Dev. = 0.67), which is above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating that this leadership approach has some positive impact, although not as strong as other styles. All the assessed factors received mean scores above the criterion mean, highlighting their role in shaping job performance among teachers.

Testing of the Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on influence of principals' democratic administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance.

Table 5: t-test analysis of responses on the influence of principals' democratic administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance

Rank	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	P. Value	Decision
Principal	493	3.16	.13	-.629	3903	0.442	Accepted
Teacher	3905	3.14	.10				

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job performance. The calculated t-value of -0.629 with 3903 degrees of freedom and the resulting p-value of 0.442 were derived. Since the p-value (0.442) is greater than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (Ho1) is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals (mean = 3.16, SD = 0.13) and teachers (mean = 3.14, SD = 0.10) regarding the influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' job performance. Both groups perceive the impact of this leadership style on job performance similarly.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on influence of principals' transactional style of leadership on teachers' job performance.

Table 6: t-test analysis of responses on the influence of principals' transactional style of leadership on teachers' job performance

Rank	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	P. Value	Decision
Principal	493	3.14	.22	-.079	3903	0.937	Accepted
Teacher	3905	3.14	.17				

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the influence of transactional leadership style on teachers' job performance. The calculated t-value of -0.079 with 3903 degrees of freedom

and the resulting p-value of 0.937 were derived. Since the p-value (0.937) is greater than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (Ho2) is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals (mean = 3.14, SD = 0.22) and teachers (mean = 3.14, SD = 0.17) regarding the influence of transactional leadership style on teachers' job performance. Both groups perceive the impact of this leadership style on job performance similarly.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on influence of principals' autocratic administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance.

Table 7: t-test analysis of responses on the influence of principals' autocratic administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance

Rank	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	P. Value	Decision
Principal	493	3.09	.12	-.117	3903	0.907	Accepted
Teacher	3905	3.10	.13				

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job performance. The calculated t-value of -0.117 with 3903 degrees of freedom and the resulting p-value of 0.907 were derived. Since the p-value (0.907) is greater than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (Ho3) is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals (mean = 3.09, SD = 0.12) and teachers (mean = 3.10, SD = 0.13) regarding the influence of autocratic leadership style on teachers' job performance. Both groups perceive the impact of this leadership style on job performance similarly.

Ho4: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings between principals and teachers on influence of principals' laissez-faire administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance.

Table 8: t-test analysis of responses on the influence of principals' laissez-faire administrative style of leadership on teachers' job performance

Rank	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	P. Value	Decision
Principal	493	2.78	.70	-.675	3903	0.436	Accepted
Teacher	3905	2.91	.57				

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the influence of laissez-faire leadership style on teachers' job performance. The calculated t-value of -0.675 with 3903 degrees of freedom and the resulting p-value of 0.436 were derived. Since the p-value (0.436) is greater than the significance level (0.05), the null hypothesis (Ho4) is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals (mean = 2.78, SD = 0.70) and teachers (mean = 2.91, SD = 0.57) regarding the influence of laissez-faire leadership style on teachers' job performance. Both groups perceive the impact of this leadership style on job performance similarly.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated principals' leadership styles and teachers' job performance in administration of secondary schools in Delta State. Key findings on research question one show that democratic leadership significantly encouraged creativity and problem solving, with group discussion, empowerment of teachers and boosting of teachers' morale as key indices. These factors are seen to expand teachers' perspectives, strengthen their innovative abilities and foster trust and

collaboration among staff. The null hypothesis was accepted. These findings are consistent with the earlier studies of Imakpokpomwan, et al. (2022) and Chinwuba (2023) who established that democratic leadership sustains team spirit in secondary school.

Key findings on research question two underscore the effectiveness of transactional leadership in fostering a structured and result-oriented environment for teachers, with managerial approach, structured guidance and discipline as key indices. These factors are seen to enhance teachers' adaptability, motivation and overall job performance. The null hypothesis two was accepted. These findings are consistent with the earlier studies of Kene, et al. (2021) and Okoroma & Agbo (2022) who established that transactional leadership style influences teachers' job performance to a high extent.

Key findings on research question three indicate autocratic leadership also influences teachers' job performance. The findings revealed that principals who adopt autocratic leadership style rarely hold discussions, thereby embarking on quick actions. The major indices include strict enforcement of rules and swift decision-taking, among others. The null hypothesis was also accepted. These findings are in tandem with the earlier studies of Adeyemi (2010) and Owenvbiugie & Ibadin (2017) who affirmed that autocratic leadership influences teachers' job performance, but only to a low extent.

Key findings on research question four indicate that the influence of laissez-faire leadership on teachers' job performance is limited but notable. The findings show that although poor relationship exists between principals and teachers in laissez-faire leadership, the minimal guidance of teachers by principals, in this style of leadership encourages teachers' independence. The null hypothesis was also accepted. These findings are in tandem with the earlier study of Maqbool (2023) who concluded that adoption of strategic leadership approach could improve and sustain academic excellence.

CONCLUSION

The success and failure of every school system depends on the type of leadership styles adopted by the principal which has impact on teachers job performance. Many organizations have failed as a result of inadequate application of leadership styles. This is evident in the findings of this study which isolated the style of leadership used by a principal as a function of teachers' job performance in school. The significant relationship found in this study between the democratic leadership style and teachers' job performance is value added. In some situations, people need to be forced before they could improve productivity. The findings of this study have therefore led the researcher to conclude that the democratic leadership style is the most accessible style of leadership that could enhance better job performance among teachers in secondary schools. However, autocratic leadership style could be chipped in when critical decisions are to be taken.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made for the study:

1. School authorities should adopt democratic leadership styles since it takes the decisions of other teachers into consideration in a school organization.
2. The autocratic leadership style should be adopted in school administration since some teachers are not willing to work before they are forced to do so.
3. Leadership style should depend on situation at hand and applied accordingly to improve teachers' job performance.
4. School organization should not adopt laissez-faire leadership style since it will lead to low teachers' job performance.

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